

Recent Advances in Battery Thermal Management Systems: Insights from the Automotive Fluids and Structural Analysis Research Laboratory (AFSARL)

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ABSTRACT

Today, the transportation electrification has become one of the hottest topics that mechanical and automotive engineers work on, and no one can cast a shadow of doubt on the fact mentioned. To widely commercialize battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), the automotive engineers have encountered a bunch of challenges, one of which is noticeably determining. The battery cooling soon after the advent of BEVs and HEVs attracted a lot of attention, and the research institution or car maker whose battery thermal management system configurations were more innovative, efficient, and also cost-effective, won the game. The Iran university of science and technology, as the only university in Iran possessing the automotive engineering faculty, has tried hard not to stay away from this hot topic, so in this review article, the most recent investigations by the automotive fluids and structural analysis research laboratory members on battery thermal management systems (BTMSs) are illustrated in brief.

1. Introduction

The automotive industry has always been one of the main topics of mechanical engineering, and no one can cast a shadow of doubt on the fact mentioned. In mid 1950s, the main challenge of the car manufacturers was the creation of internal combustion engines whose overall efficiency could be acceptable and fuel consumption per mile could be competitive. After the crude oil crisis in mid 1980s, the world moved towards independence from fossil fuels, and that was the birth, development and commercialization of the vehicles running partly or entirely on electricity.

The key factor that played the most important role in commercialization of battery electric vehicles and hybrid electric vehicles was the energy source of them, i.e., the batteries. Soon after the application of batteries as the energy source for the electric transportation, experts

found out that the heat generated by the battery has to be removed out of the battery pack, else the battery may experience thermal runaway due to the accumulated heat. This was the time when the initial battery thermal management systems were designed and applied in green transportation industry.

In this paper, the authors try to represent and review the recent investigations conducted by the researchers of automotive fluids and structural analysis research laboratory, better known as AFSARL, located in school of automotive engineering of the Iran university of science and technology. In what follows, the authors review the majority of published articles related to the field of battery thermal management systems, believing that this paper might be useful for those who want to get acquainted with the research line of the aforementioned laboratory. At the end, the Authors express their thankfulness to all lab

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members without whose research this paper could have never been written.

2. Why Do Batteries Need Cooling?

As mentioned before, the batteries are the main energy source of the green transportation, and no one can reject the fact mentioned. The use of batteries as the backbone of electric vehicle industry has always been a challenge since the batteries are so sensitive to the temperature. The environmental temperature or the battery surface temperature directly affects the battery performance and as a result, the vehicle mileage is affected.

The batteries generate heat while being discharged and this is the nature of them. They consist of positive tab, electrolyte and the negative tab, and while the discharging process, the chemical reaction within the battery generates heat. One should note that the higher the discharge rate becomes, the greater dissipated heat from the battery is experienced. For instance, Salami Ranjbaran et al. [1] investigated the thermal behavior of the commercial prismatic lithium battery cells applied in electrified transportation. Using the multi scale multi dimensional model (MSMD), they numerically simulated the battery full discharge process from 100% state of the charge (SOC) to zero at four different C-rates, 1C, 2C, 3C, and 4C. They reported that the maximum surface temperature of the battery has a close relation with the discharge rate (C-rate). They reported that The maximum battery surface temperature at the end of the simulation reaches 308.6 K, 318.3 K, 325.5 K, and 330.6 K for 1C, 2C, 3C, and 4C discharge rates, respectively, showing that the battery needs to be cooled down if the thermal runaway needs to be avoided.

Fig 1. Temperature of the cell at the end of 4C discharge rate reported by Salami Ranjbaran [1].

In particular, the necessity of battery thermal management presence becomes more and more vital if higher C-rates are experienced by the

battery, i.e., noticeable acceleration is demanded by the vehicle driver. Nemati et al. [2] also investigated the battery thermal behavior and voltage variation versus time for even much higher C-rates, 7C and 9C rates of discharge. They reported that the maximum surface temperature greater than 337 K is experienced which could create a remarkable challenge for the automotive car manufacturers.

Fig 2. Temperature variation of a battery cell for different discharge rates reported by Nemati [2]

All the paragraphs above are mentioned to reach this end that the battery embodied within the hybrid electric vehicle should not be left on its own and a sophisticated thermal management system needs to be installed to remove the generated heat. If not, the battery calendar life is decreased and in some severe cases, thermal explosions are observed.

3. Different Types of Battery Thermal Management Systems

Battery thermal management systems are categorized based on the dependency or independency to energy usage for running the battery thermal management system. Active battery thermal management systems are those whose application uses energy supplied by the vehicle. One of the most common types of active cooling techniques is the application of blown cold air throughout the battery pack. This type of cooling needs electricity to be run, and requires a fan, duct and condenser-evaporator to operate. Another type of active cooling method is the application of water circulation within the tubes having direct connection with the battery surface. This method is categorized within the active category since the system uses energy to run the pump, leading to circulation of cooled water within the battery pack.

Passive battery thermal management systems are those independent of energy demand from the vehicle to operate. In other words, they do not use any energy to operate, and as a result, increase the

vehicle overall mileage. One of the most common techniques of passive battery thermal management system application is the use of phase change materials, better known as PCMs. The phase change materials use the benefit of high latent heat value, absorbing dissipated heat from the battery and getting liquid (transferring their state of phase from entirely solid to entirely/partly liquid). This material is poured within the specific zones inside the battery pack, and since they do not use any bit of energy to operate, they are called passive battery thermal management systems.

If more information about the development of battery thermal management system and the journey from simple pure BTMS to hybrid complex ones is needed, it is suggested that the researcher refer to the review paper by Bamdezh et al. [3] whose review writing and accuracy is remarkably good. The authors of this paper with Dr. Mohammadali Bamdezh the best in his personal and academic life.

4. Recent Advances in Completely Active Battery Thermal Management Systems

As mentioned above, active battery thermal management systems are those whose applications are dependent on energy usage. They use energy supplied by the vehicle to operate, and have some benefits, too. They are controllable, meaning that the strength of the battery thermal management system is altered by the vehicle central processing unit (CPU) so that the safe battery operating temperature is maintained. Investigations on purely active battery thermal management systems are so limited, and here, authors can only refer to the article by Jalil et al. [4] as the only example. Jalil et al. applied the pulsating heat pump method to the battery pack to investigate its efficiency in battery cooling. They applied Horizontal Pulsating Heat Pump (H-PHP), Vertical Pulsating Heat Pump (V-PHP), and Inclined Pulsating Heat Pump (I-PHP). They reported that the shift from I-PHP or H-PHP to V-PHP would result in a decrease in thermal resistance values by 50% and 38%, respectively.

The authors believe that the application of active battery thermal management systems within the battery packs is a hot field, whose importance have been neglected by the lab members, and advise them to investigate more on the field mentioned. Although this method is not that much favorable due to energy usage and vehicle mileage reduction, the BTMS controllability and better cooling results are not

the items letting the researcher forget about the air-cooled battery thermal management system.

Fig 3. Experimental case setup by Jalil [4]

5. Recent Investigations on Fully Passive Battery Thermal Management Systems

The fully passive battery thermal management systems are those whose applications are not based on the energy usage. Those systems are dependent on a thermophysical benefit to operate and this is both a merit and a demerit. The advantage of application of passive battery thermal management systems is the vehicle mileage increase due to zero energy consumption, but the disadvantage is more noticeable. These systems are hardly controllable and most of the time, they are unlikely to be beneficial if the environmental temperature soars harshly. In addition, the passive BTMS most of the time suffer from significantly low thermal conductivity meaning that the system might not be a good candidate to be applied for severe driving conditions.

At the automotive fluids and structural analysis research laboratory, there are some invaluable investigations on the application of phase change materials within the battery packs of the electric vehicles. The phase change materials use the benefit of great noticeable latent heat value, liquefying while absorbing heat. They were considered to be one of the best candidates of passive battery thermal management systems since they maintained the battery temperature within the safe limit surprisingly using no energy. Jenabi Haghparast [5] investigated the application of phase change material based battery thermal management systems for the battery pack of an electric vehicle. They reported that the application of PCM-based BTMS maintains the battery temperature within the safe limit, and also reducing the maximum temperature gradient significantly, which shows the good application of PCM-Based BTMS. They also reported that the PCM-based BTMS suffers from low thermal

conductivity, whose symptoms were perfectly obvious in their experimental investigations.

Fig 4. Experimental setup by Jenabi Hagharast [5]

PCM low thermal conductivity is one of the most important challenges of its application. In order to tackle such a challenge, one may use some thermal conductivity enhancement techniques. One of the most common methods to increase PCM low thermal conductivity is the application of extended surfaces (better known as metal fins) to help battery dissipate its heat more efficiently, and to help PCM better absorb dissipated heat. Shojaeefard et al. [6] investigated the role of metal fin addition to the PCM, investigating how fin alignment affects the PCM mushy zone break down manner. They reported that the horizontal fin configuration has the best performance due to lowest PCM melt fraction and best PCM mushy zone configurations.

Fig 5. Numerical simulation setup by Shojaeefard [6]

Application of metal porous foams to the PCM zone is another way one can increase the low thermal conductivity of PCM. Salami Ranjbaran et al. [7] investigated the role of Copper foam insertion within the pure PCM zone, studying how it would effect the PCM melt behavior and mushy zone configuration. They added a variety of Cu foam, from 1% volumetric percentage to 10%, looking for improvement. They reported that the 6% of volumetric fraction represents the best

PCM liquid fraction and battery surface temperature. For more information on the buoyancy effect on PCM melt behavior and liquid mushy zone configuration, one may refer to reference by Shojaeefard Salami Ranjbaran et al. [8] whose readership is so much fruitful.

Fig 6. Numerical simulation setup by Ranjbaran [7]

6. Why is the Hybrid Battery Thermal Management System the Solution?

The hybrid battery thermal management system is the combination of both active and passive battery thermal management systems, aiming to take advantage of the pros of each system and to mitigate each ones' drawbacks. Most of the battery thermal management system engineers try to mix active cooling techniques such as cool air blowing or cold liquid circulation with passive battery thermal management systems based on PCM to reach better outcomes, and our lab at the school of automotive engineering is no exception. In what follows, the authors briefly represent recent works on hybrid battery thermal management systems.

The first type of investigations is the hybrid battery thermal management systems possessing the air cooling system and the PCM-based systems. The air cooling systems helps PCM withstand liquefying rapidly experiencing harsh conditions such as high C-rates of discharge. Moreover, the PCM-based system helps the air cooling systems by reducing the battery surface temperature gradient, which is the fatal drawback of the active air-cooled BTMS.

For instance, Molaeimanesh et al. [9] investigated a hybrid battery thermal management performance owning PCM and cooling air circulation ducts. They investigated the role of configuration on the performance of the BTMS and the PCM liquid fraction behavior during the whole simulation period. They mentioned that the parallel configuration of the batteries can strongly maintain the cells within the safe temperature,

meeting the automotive manufacturing demands. Continuing this investigation, Bamdezh et al. [10] profoundly investigated the role of system structure and how the parallel or zigzag battery configurations react to blown air and how the PCM liquid fraction manner changes with configuration alteration. The module compactness and the PCM ring thickness were also other items they tried to work on. They reported that for all numerically simulated cases, the battery temperature and the maximum battery surface temperature gradient is located within the safe limit, showing the efficiency of the hybrid battery thermal management system.

Fig 7. Final comments reported by Bamdezh [10]

Salami Ranjbaran et al. [11] investigated the role of cooling air duct shapes within the hybrid battery thermal management system based on PCM. The duct shapes were two-passageways, three-passageways and four-passageways, and also the blown cold air strength were altered. They reported that the designed systems maintain the battery within the safe temperature limit, the maximum temperature gradient is acceptable even for the worst case scenario and the PCM melt behavior is noticeably controlled due to the help given by the cooling air duct. Following the aforementioned research, Sajedi et al. [12] experimentally investigated the fin addition to a hybrid battery thermal management system based on refrigerated cooling air and the phase change material. The fin shapes were spiral, axial and radial, and also the environmental conditions were changed to play a role. They reported that for the harsh environmental conditions, the pure passive battery thermal management system cannot operate efficiently, showing the importance of being helped by an active cooling BTMS. Furthermore, they reported that the pure active cooling system based on cooling air circulation suffers from a great maximum surface temperature gradient, representing the need for a passive BTMS to mitigate this issue.

Fig 8. PCM liquid fraction contourplots reported by Salami Ranjbaran et al. [11]

The other type of battery cooling technique hybridization is the combination of a passive PCM-based battery thermal management system with the the cooling liquid circulation systems. The cooling liquid system helps PCM tolerate harsh conditions, preventing it from liquefying so rapidly, and on the other hand, the PCM-based BTMS helps liquid cooling method to mitigate the unacceptable maximum surface temperature gradient in severe conditions. Bamdezh et al. [13] investigated the role of foam anisotropy within a hybrid battery thermal management system owning liquid cooling channels and PCM. One should note that adding metal foams to pure PCM results in phase change composite material, enhancing its thermal conductivity. The foam anisotropy here means the radial foam, axial foam and also the tangential foam are applied to investigate which represent the best PCM thermal conductivity enhancement. They reported that the tangential foam configuration shows the best thermophysical performance, maintaining the battery cell within the most optimum temperature range.

Fig 8. Experimental case setup by Sajedi [12]

Following this path, Hekamt et al. [14] conceptually designed and numerically simulated a hybrid battery thermal management system

based on PCM and the water circulation channels to achieve extremely uniform battery surface temperature distribution within a battery pack of an electric vehicle. They also altered the battery discharge rates and coolant flow rates, and finally reported that the battery surface temperature, maximum surface temperature gradient and PCM liquid fraction behavior is completely safe. More information on this work can be found referring to the reference [15].

Fig 8. Proposed hybrid battery thermal management system by Hekmat et al. [14]

The research on hybrid battery thermal management systems based on liquid cooling and PCM-based systems are not limited to what mentioned above, but for the sake of keeping this paper short and informative, one may refer to the investigations on hybrid BTMS based on silicone oil and water channel cooling by Hekmat et al. [16], role of water channel configuration on the performance of hybrid battery thermal management system based on PCM and liquid cooling by Molaeimanesh et al. [17], and finally the role of mini channel incorporation within the hybrid battery thermal management systems based on water cooling and PCM-based medium by Hekmat et al. [18]. The authors wish Dr. Shahriyar Hekmat the sweetest and the most invaluable success along with his academic and personal journey.

In addition, reading of the references mentioned at the end of this paragraph is proposed for those who want to gain excessive information on the topic this paper is about [19,20].

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